

INFORMED CONSENT FORM (ICF)

Research Title: "**Method to Support Digital Game Development Using User Experience (UX)**"

Researcher(s) or other professional responsible for the research, with Addresses and Telephone Numbers:

Prof. Dr. Renato Balancieri - rbalancieri@uem.br - (44) 98836-0018

Prof^a. Dr^a Gislaïne Camila Lapasini Leal - gclleal@uem.br - (44) 9990-1646 Felipe

Fernandes da Silva – pg55749@uem.br (44) 99933-0509

Researchers from the Graduate Program in Computer Science – PPC, at the State University of Maringá – Av. Colombo, 5790 - Zona 7, Maringá - PR, 87020-900.

Research Location: The research will be conducted on a digital platform, online, made available via a link that will be sent through social media to the participants.

A) INFORMATION TO THE PARTICIPANT

You are being invited to voluntarily participate in the research "Method to Support Digital Game Development Using User Experience (UX)". The following questionnaire is part of a doctoral research project from the Graduate Program in Computer Science at the State University of Maringá - UEM - Main Campus Maringá. Your collaboration is free and voluntary, and participating in the research by completing the questionnaire is of fundamental importance for the development and completion of this study.

You may choose not to participate in the research, withdraw at any time, and, if necessary, request further clarification. We also assure that the confidentiality and anonymity of the research participants will be maintained.

This research has been submitted to the Research Ethics Committee of the State University of Maringá – UEM, and its development is the responsibility of the researcher under the supervision of Prof. Dr. Renato Balancieri.

1. Presentation of the research

The development of digital games has evolved rapidly in recent years, and one of the main factors contributing to a game's success is the quality of the experience offered to the user. User Experience (UX) is an approach that places the player at the center of the creation process, seeking to understand their expectations, needs, and behaviors in order to design more intuitive, engaging, and satisfying interactions. In this context, the application of UX techniques in digital game development becomes a competitive differentiator, directly impacting player retention and engagement.

This research aims to structure, define, and systematize a method for digital game development focused on UX, analyzing how user-centered practices influence the creative process and final outcomes. By integrating stages such as rapid prototyping, usability testing, and feedback analysis, UX-driven development enables continuous adjustments and improvements, resulting in an experience more aligned with players' expectations.

Furthermore, the research will investigate how development teams can incorporate UX into their daily practices, from the initial game concept through the testing and refinement phases, ensuring that the final product not only works technically but also provides an enjoyable and intuitive journey for the user.

The application of UX principles in game development offers a more targeted and efficient approach, allowing developers to quickly adjust design flaws and improve key aspects of gameplay. Furthermore, the focus on user experience enables greater player retention and an increase in overall satisfaction with the product.

This research contributes to the advancement of knowledge in the field by examining how the integration of UX techniques can not only improve gameplay but also influence strategic decisions in game development. Based on case studies and analyses of real projects, the work offers practical insights into the challenges and opportunities of using UX as an essential tool in digital game development.

2. Research objectives

The objective of the research is to investigate the UX practices and tools used in the development of digital games.

Among the research objectives are:

- a) To evaluate the perception of studios and developers regarding the importance of using UX in the digital game development process, covering both fundamental concepts and practical applications.
- b) To investigate how studios and developers understand and value the integration of UX into their product development process.
- c) To identify possible barriers or challenges perceived by professionals regarding the adoption of UX in digital game development.

3. Participation in the research

Your participation in the research consists of completing an online questionnaire via an access link to Google Forms. The first page available in Google Forms will contain the Informed Consent Form (ICF), in which the research participant must agree and give consent (mandatory requirement) to complete the data collection instrument, which is the questionnaire to be administered.

Without the participant's proper acceptance and agreement to the ICF, it is not possible to proceed to the other pages that make up the questionnaire. Through Google Forms, it is possible to print the form for signatures and/or take screenshots of the screens. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, agreement and acceptance are considered sufficient, and signatures are waived.

The responses to this questionnaire will enable an understanding of the attributes needed to comprehend the UX practices adopted and the reasons for not adopting them in digital game development. The research consists of questions mainly related to UX concepts and understanding of the studio's development process, as well as questions regarding the respondent's profile. The estimated time to complete the questionnaire is approximately 10 minutes (this time may vary depending on each participant).

4. Confidentiality

The research participant will be guaranteed privacy and data confidentiality, with the data obtained in the research remaining under the responsibility of the researchers. Thus, the participant is assured that none of their data will, under any circumstances, be disclosed, as the responses will be absolutely confidential.

It will also be guaranteed that all participants will have their social, cultural, moral, religious, and ethical values, as well as their habits and customs, fully respected during the research. Furthermore, considering that the research will be conducted in a virtual environment, it is emphasized that the information will not be used to promote the offering of products or services, in accordance with Google Forms' privacy policy terms, ensuring that the confidentiality and secrecy of the information provided to the responsible researcher will be maintained.

5. Risks and Benefits

Specifically, the research titled "Method to Support Digital Game Development Using User Experience (UX)" seeks to identify aspects related to the understanding of digital game industry professionals regarding the importance of concepts related to this topic. Thus, the existing risks and benefits to the respondents of this research will be presented.

5a) Risks:

The research uses a questionnaire as its data collection instrument, which may cause, in some individuals, certain negative experiences when faced with specific questions, such as invasion of privacy, stress, tiredness or annoyance when answering, embarrassment or discomfort, taking up the participant's time to respond, shame or fear of being identified, changes in self-esteem or worldview, relationships and behaviors, and the risk of breach of confidentiality.

Therefore, certain measures have been adopted, such as: careful preparation of the content of the questions to avoid any type of embarrassment, discomfort, and negative experiences; measures to prevent fatigue during the questionnaire completion process; and cultural, social, moral, religious, and ethical values have always been respected in the questionnaire's development. Furthermore, the questionnaire can be answered wherever and whenever the participant wishes, in a private setting, to minimize discomfort and embarrassment.

Participants are informed that they may stop the research at any time if any type of discomfort or embarrassment arises.

The responses will be absolutely confidential, and each questionnaire will not allow the identification of the individual, so that anonymity is maintained. Furthermore, the study will be suspended immediately upon perceiving any risk or harm to the research participant that was not foreseen in the consent form.

In addition to the risks and benefits related to participation in the research, attention is drawn to the risks characteristic of the virtual environment, risks that are inherent due to the limitations of the technology used. The researchers guarantee the confidentiality of the information, confidentiality and privacy, but the risk of breach of confidentiality may occur involuntarily and unintentionally.

5b) Benefits:

As a benefit of the study, the respondent will contribute to identifying the main challenges and needs of professionals regarding the use of UX in their product development process, a fact that helps find solutions, innovation, and improvements for digital game development. The research enables game studios and developers to have a foundation for developing their products, prioritizing attributes that increase user satisfaction for this purpose.

6. Inclusion and exclusion criteria**6a) Inclusion:**

The individuals participating in the research must be professionals working in the field of digital game development and game development studios, be Brazilian, and be over 18 years of age.

6b) Exclusion:

Not applicable.

7. Right to withdraw from the research and to receive clarification during the process

Research participants have the right to:

- Refuse to participate in the research;
- Withdraw from the study at any time;
- Receive any clarification about the research, at any stage.
- Withdraw their consent to participate at any time, without any penalty. In this case, the responsible researcher will send the research participant an acknowledgment of the participant's interest in withdrawing their consent.

The results of the questionnaire will be published in the Doctoral research resulting from this study. You may check the field below to receive the results of this research, should you be interested:

- I want to receive the research results (email for sending: _____)
- I do not want to receive the research results

It is emphasized that it is important for the research participant to keep an electronic copy of this document in their files, to ensure that their rights are protected and for any questions that may arise after completing the questionnaire.

8. Reimbursement and compensation

The research is conducted online and does not generate any cost to the study participant. Therefore, there will be no reimbursement, as the research does not incur any expenses for the participant, such as transportation or food costs. However, the participant is entitled to compensation. Thus, material coverage will be provided to remedy any harm caused to the research participant by the study.

CLARIFICATIONS ABOUT THE RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE:

The Research Ethics Committee Involving Human Beings (COPEP/UEM) is composed of a team of professionals with multidisciplinary training who work to ensure respect for your rights as a research participant. Its objective is to assess whether the research has been planned and will be conducted ethically. If you believe that the research is not being carried out as you were informed, or that you are being harmed in any way, please contact the Research Ethics Committee Involving Human Beings at the State University of Maringá (COPEP/UEM). Address: Av. Colombo, 5790 - Zona 7, Maringá - PR, 87020-900. Phone: (44) 3011-4597 e-mail: copep@uem.br

B) CONSENT

I declare that I have knowledge of the information contained in this document and have received clear answers to my questions regarding my direct (or indirect) participation in the research, and additionally, I declare that I have understood the objective, nature, risks, benefits, reimbursement, and compensation related to this study.

() I declare that I have decided, freely and voluntarily, to participate in this study. I am also aware that I may leave the project at any time, without any penalty.

() I do not wish to participate in the research.

To receive the Informed Consent Form (ICF), please leave your email address:

We declare that we have presented the study, explaining its objectives, nature, risks, and benefits, and that we have answered the questions asked to the best of our ability.

Prof. Dr. Renato Balancieri - rbalancieri@uem.br - (44) 98836-0018

Felippe Fernandes da Silva – pg55749@uem.br (44) 99933-0509

For all questions regarding the study or to withdraw from it, you may contact any of the researchers via email or telephone. Contact the Research Ethics Committee involving human beings for complaints, appeals, or grievances from the research participant:

Permanent Committee for Research Ethics Involving Human Beings at UEM (COPEP): Av. Colombo, 5790, PPG, room 4, ZIP Code 87020-900. Maringá - PR. Phone: (44) 3011-4597, e-mail: copep@uem.br

City: _____

Date: _____